

Imaging Methods for In-Situ Structural Health Monitoring

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Abstract

This paper presents a beamforming method for imaging structural damages by using a network of active sensors, which provides a rapid mapping technique for in-situ structural health monitoring. By sequentially scanning the structure through exciting one sensor and receiving with the others, before and after the presence of structural damages, a qualitative image of the damaged structure can be constructed based on the sensor responses to the scattered waves by using the digital beamforming principle. From the coarse image, potential damage areas can be identified and their approximate locations determined, which would enable continuous monitoring to detect increases in damage size. Furthermore, the information gained from this coarse image provides the basis for a quantitative imaging method, such as computerized tomography.

Introduction

In-situ structural health monitoring techniques being developed under the general heading of smart materials and structures holds considerable promise for a significant improvement in the design and management of composite structures, which are often susceptible to delamination or even fiber fracture when subjected to impact damage or normal service loading. In this regard, considerable progress [1, 2] has been made in developing systems based on distributed active sensors, such as piezoelectric transducers, which are either surface mounted or integrally imbedded. Since one major aim of an in-situ structural health monitoring system is to determine the location, size, shape, and severity of structural damages, it would be advantageous to develop a quantitative imaging technique that could create a detailed map of the damage status of the structure being monitored, as illustrated in Fig.1. Such an imaging system will not only provide a convenient heads-up display that continuously tracks the evolution of damages, but also facilitate prognostic analysis to determine residual strength.

A significant challenge to the development of a quantitative imaging method for in-situ structural health monitoring system is that only a relatively small number of active sensors could be embedded due to economic or practicality constraints. This low sensor-density coupled with the small field-ratio (ratio of damage size to sensor spacing) means that it is necessary to develop an iterative imaging approach. Firstly a coarse image is created which can be used to ascertain the approximate location of potential damages. Then, by using synthetic time-reversal method [3, 4] it

would be possible to focus the energy of the entire sensor network onto the damages identified in the first step to enable a quantitative image to be generated. As a first step towards this goal, this paper presents an imaging method based on the digital beamforming principle for constructing coarse images; quantitative imaging methods will be presented elsewhere.

Fig.1 An in-situ diagnostic imaging and prognostics system.

This paper is structured as below. The digital beamforming method is first outlined, which is then followed by a description of an in-situ health monitoring experiment. Images from the digital beamforming method will be compared with the actual specimen with simulating damages. The beamforming method is an array signal processing technique that was initially developed for radar systems [5] but has been successfully adapted in other fields, including sonar systems, wireless communications [6, 7], and ultrasound imaging [8]. In the present paper, the potential of the digital beamforming method as an in-situ structural health monitoring technique for mapping structural damages is demonstrated by comparing the results with the constructed images with the experimental results.

Basics of Digital Beamforming Method

Consider a structure with a distributed network of active sensors (such as piezoelectric transducers) as shown in Fig.2. Since each active sensor can act as both transmitter and receiver, a sequential scan of the structure can be performed by exciting one sensor at a time with a controlled diagnostic signal, such as a narrow-band tone-burst, which is denoted as $p(t)$. The received signals at the other array elements represent the stress waves arriving at the sensor location. In the absence of structural damage, these signals serve as the base-line data, which may contain the direct component of the stress wave radiating from the actuator and reflected/diffracted waves by structural features, such as stiffeners. The same scan can be carried out periodically when the structure is in service, with the resulting signals containing both the base-line data and the scattered waves caused by the presence of structural damages. Subtracting the base-line data from

the total responses gives the scattered signals, which are basically the sensor responses to the radiated waves from the damages being illuminated by the incident waves.

Fig. 2 An in-situ structural health monitoring system with distributed active sensors.

The beamforming method is essentially to first multiple the scattered signals by weight coefficients and then sum up the weighted signal to yield an array output that is focused in a particular angular direction. By making use of the time-of-flight information of the diagnostic pulse, spatial location in terms of the distance of the target to a reference sensor can be determined. To illustrate the working principles of this method, consider a distributed sensor network consisting of N transducers, their positions being denoted as (x_i, y_i) , $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. Denote the base-line data and the total response received by sensor n when sensor m is excited as $f_{mn}^{(i)}(t)$ and $f_{mn}(t)$, respectively. The scattered signal for this actuator-sensor path, as shown in Fig.3, is then given by

$$f_{mn}^{(s)}(t) = f_{mn}(t) - f_{mn}^{(i)}(t). \quad (1)$$

Since each active sensor can act either as an actuator or a sensor at any one time, there are a total of $N(N-1)$ different paths available for the entire sensor array. However, due to reciprocal theory, there are only half independent paths. To determine the total time-of-flight for the signal to travel from the actuator to the sensor location, the scattered signal can be cross-correlated with the actuation signal $p(t)$,

$$C_{mn}(t) = \int_0^T f_{mn}^{(s)}(\tau) p(\tau+t) d\tau. \quad (2)$$

Then the contrast at an arbitrary imaging point can be determined by [9],

$$I(x, y) = \sum_{m=1}^N \sum_{n=m+1}^N A_{mn} C_{mn}^{(a)} \left(\frac{R_s + R_a}{c_g} \right), \quad (3)$$

where the superscript a refers to the amplitude of the cross-correlated signal. This amplitude at any time instance can be determined by interpolating between the maxim and minima (turning points), e.g., using spline-fit, of the cross-correlated signal. The parameter c_g denotes the group velocity of the controlled diagnostic signal, R_s and R_a the distances from the imaging point to the received (sensor n) and actuator (sensor m), respectively, as shown in Fig.3. The parameters A_{mn} refer to the appropriate aperture weighting to each actuator-sensor pair, which in the simplest case would be equal to unity for uniform sensor aperture. In practice, to reduce the effect of the variations in sensor sensitivity among the sensor array, the aperture weighting can be taken to be inversely proportional to the peak amplitude of the base-line data, viz,

$$A_{mn} = \frac{1}{\max(f_{mn}^{(i)}(t))}. \quad (4)$$

Since the maximum resolution of any sensor array is limited by the diffraction limit, which is equal to half wavelength of the incident waves, it would sufficient to set the smallest pixel size to half the wavelength at the center frequency of the tone-burst signal.

Fig. 3 Imaging by the beamforming method.

Experimental Method

To demonstrate the potential of the digital beamforming method described in the previous section, a series of experiments were conducted on a flat panel made of aluminium alloy (thickness=1 mm). Four piezoelectric sensors (diameter=6.35 mm, thickness=0.25 mm) were surface mounted as shown in Fig.4. The electro-mechanical properties of the piezoelectric material (APC850) are available from the manufacturer [10]. To simulate the scattering effect of structural damages to guided waves, cylindrical masses of varying diameters were bonded to the specimen at different locations. Three examples are shown in Fig.5 together with the images obtained by the digital beamforming method. The experiments were carried out by exciting each of the four sensors with a tone-burst having a center frequency of 200 KHz, while responses were recorded at the other

three sensors. Altogether there are twelve possible actuator-sensor paths. If we ignore the boundary reflections, only six combinations are independent. However, because of the relatively small size of the panel specimen, whose four edges were free of constraints, strong boundary reflections were observed. Therefore, signals from all the twelve paths were employed in the digital beamforming process.

Fig. 4 A plate specimen with four active sensors.

As can be seen in equation (3), the only additional information that is required for the digital imaging method is the group velocity c_g , which can be determined either by Lamb solution, or more conveniently the Mindlin plate theory [9, 11-13]. It is also possible to experimentally determine the group velocity from the base-line data, since the distances between sensors are known. Since all the sensors are surface mounted, at the chosen testing frequency the induced guided waves in the plate were mainly flexural, with the amplitude of the sensor response to the extensional wave being one quarter that of the flexural wave. Therefore, in the following analysis only the flexural wave component will be considered. In this case, the Mindlin plate theory gives a group velocity of 2275 m/s for the flexural wave at the frequency of 200 KHz , very close to the experimental value. The corresponding the wavelength of the flexural wave is 6.5 mm .

The comparisons shown in Figs.5 demonstrate that the basic beamforming method is able to correctly image the location of the scatterer (indicated by a black circle), whether it is located inside or outside the boundary of the sensor array. However, the size of the scatterer was not very well resolved. This could be attributed to several factors, including the duration of the pulse, which limits the maximum spatial resolution to be around twice the wavelength, or 13 mm , which is approximately the size of the smallest scatterer shown in Fig.5(c).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 5 Comparisons between actual scatterers and images created by digital beamforming method; (a) one large scatterer (diameter=42.5mm) (b) a medium scatterer (diameter=20.5mm) and (c) a small scatterer (diameter=12.5mm).

Discussion

In the above analysis the image intensity is proportional to the amplitude of the cross-correlation between the scattered signal and the actuation pulse. An alternative formulation is to relate image intensity to the power flux (per unit length along the wave front), which is proportional to the square of the measured surface strain [12]. In this case, the image intensity is given by,

$$I(x, y) = \sum_{m=1}^N \sum_{n=m+1}^N A_{mn} \left[C_{mn}^{(a)} \left(\frac{R_s + R_a}{c_g} \right) \right]^2. \quad (5)$$

This new formulation has the effect of sharpening the image around the scatterer. As an example, new images for the three cases considered in Fig.5 are shown in Fig.6. It is can be seen that the power-flux based method increased the contrast and resulted in smaller spot-size for the scatterer as compared to the amplitude-based beamforming method.

It should be noted that the present beamforming method implicitly assumes that the damage has an isotropic scattering pattern, and the wave amplitude does not vary with distance. Recent results on the scattering of plate waves by structural damages [14] suggest that these two assumptions may introduce considerable errors, especially when the wavelength is small comparable to damage size. Further work would be required to develop an adaptive beamforming method that will take into account of these effects.

Fig.6 Images using power-flux based beamforming method.

Conclusions

To develop a damage mapping method suitable for active in-situ structural health monitoring, the digital beamforming method has been extended to image structural damages that scatter/diffract guided waves. Comparison with experimental results demonstrates that the linear digital beamforming technique provides a robust imaging method for locating damages within as well as outside the boundary of the sensor array.

The present method provides a rapid mapping technique for in-situ structural health monitoring, which can be used to locate damages and to qualitatively monitor damage size. The coarse image created by this beamforming technique also provides the basis for an advanced imaging method that could produce images of higher resolution.

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